

Equilibrium of the dinuclear complex formation between organotin(IV) and metal-Schiff base complexes in solution

Maryam Mohammadikish^{a*}, Zahra Seyedzadeh^b and Mozaffar Asadi^c

^aFaculty of Chemistry, Kharazmi University, Tehran, Iran

E-mail : mohammadikish@yahoo.com Fax : 98-26-34551023

^bChemistry Department, Faculty of Sciences, Kermanshah Branch, Islamic Azad University, Kermanshah, Iran

^cChemistry Department, College of Sciences, Shiraz University, Shiraz, Iran

Manuscript received online 19 January 2012, revised 24 March 2012, accepted 10 May 2012

Abstract : A UV-Vis spectrophotometric study of the adduct formation of $M^{II}(\text{salabza})$, $M^{II}(5\text{-OMe-salabza})$, $M^{II}(5\text{-Br-salabza})$ and $M^{II}(5\text{-NO}_2\text{-salabza})$ (where $M = \text{Co}, \text{Cu}$ and $\text{salabza-H}_2 = N,N'$ -bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzylamine) as donor with Me_2SnCl_2 , Ph_2SnCl_2 , $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and Ph_4Sn as acceptor has been investigated in DMF. Formation constants and Gibbs free energies were measured for 1 : 1 adduct at 25 °C. The data refinement was carried out with the SQUAD 84 program. The trend of formation constants of metal Schiff base complex with organotin(IV) compounds follows the order :

Keywords : Formation constant, cobalt, copper, Schiff base complex, tin adduct.

Introduction

Previously, other groups have shown that tin(IV) Lewis acids form 1 : 1 adducts with transition metal Schiff base complexes¹⁻¹³. The divalent metal salicylaldimine complexes represent a fascinating group of ligands, which have been shown to display a number of chelating modes. The disposition of the 3-methoxy and phenolic oxygens in the investigated complexes is in strong favor of hydrogen bonding interactions with water, and this hydrogen bonded water may then forms a donor bond to a Lewis acid such as dimethyltin(IV) dichloride or triphenyltin(IV) chloride⁴⁻⁶. Also, a metal can be located within the plane of the phenolic and methoxy oxygens, where it is held by donor bonds from these atoms^{2,7}.

The adducts of vanadyl(IV) Schiff base complexes with diorganotin(IV) dichloride and triorganotin(IV) chloride have been investigated by Ng *et al.*^{12,13}. In these adducts vanadyl oxygen acts as donor atom to tin center and tin has trigonal bipyramidal geometry. Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions in acetonitrile solution were found to form the

1 : 1 adducts with transition metal Schiff base complexes¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Inada *et al.*¹⁷ has determined the rate constants and stability constants of the complex formation of Cu(salen) with metal (I,II) ions in acetonitrile.

The structure of these adducts with Schiff base complexes has been thoroughly explored in the solid state^{2,5-7,10,11}, very little is known about their formation equilibrium in solution. Except our previous works¹⁸⁻²⁴, there is no other report about the investigation of formation constants of the dinuclear complexes resulted from reaction between Schiff base metal complexes with an N_2O_2 ligand and organotin(IV) compounds in solution. In this study, tetradentate Schiff base cobalt and copper complexes, $M^{II}(\text{salabza})$, ($\text{salabza-H}_2 = N,N'$ -bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzylamine and its derivatives) (Scheme 1) have been used as ligands in order to investigate the equilibrium constant for the formation of dinuclear complex with tin(IV) compounds (Me_2SnCl_2 , Bu_2SnCl_2 , Ph_2SnCl_2 and Ph_4Sn) in N,N' -dimethylformamide (DMF).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Formation constants, Gibbs free energy calculations and stoichiometry evaluation :

The complex formation constants, K_{av} (Table 1), were calculated using the SQUAD computer program^{25,26}, which was designed to calculate the best value for the formation constants of the proposed equation model (given below) by employing a non-linear, least-squares approach.

$n = m = 2$, R = Me, Ph, n-Bu or $n = 4$, $m = 0$,
R = Ph

M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}

L²⁻ = deprotonated tetradentate Schiff base = salabza

The free energy change ΔG^\ddagger (Table 2) of the formed complexes were calculated from $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$ at 25 °C.

The relationship obtained for the molar ratio (MR) method are characterized by one break at molar ratio [Sn]/[ML] = 1. This behavior clearly indicates that the stoichiometry of resulted dinuclear complexes from the reaction of the organotin(IV) compounds with metal Schiff base complexes in the solution is 1 : 1 (Sn : ML).

Also, crystal structures of similar salen type compounds (salen = *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)ethylenediamine), proved the presence of 1 : 1 adduct in the solid state^{5,6,10,12}. Considering previous researches show that the connection mode of the tin atom to Schiff base can be investigated in two class : First, each of these compounds are organotin aqua adducts with donor water molecule engaged in hydrogen bonding interactions with the phenolic oxygen atoms of the divalent metal Schiff base^{5,6,11}. Indeed, the two phenolic oxygen atoms in the essentially planner [M(salabza)] should bind to the water solvated tin ions. Secondly, the metal salicylaldimine can act as

Table 1. The formation constants, K_{av} (L mol⁻¹), for the metal Schiff base complexes with organotin compounds in DMF solvent at 25 °C

	Me ₂ SnCl ₂	Ph ₂ SnCl ₂	Bu ₂ SnCl ₂	Ph ₄ Sn
[Co(5-OMe-salabza)].H ₂ O	3.29 (±0.10)	3.21 (±0.03)	2.67 (±0.01)	2.61 (±0.15)
[Co(salabza)].2H ₂ O	2.45 (±0.04)	2.41 (±0.06)	2.31 (±0.05)	2.05 (±0.31)
[Co(5-Br-salabza)].H ₂ O	2.35 (±0.39)	2.10 (±0.03)	2.05 (±0.04)	1.97 (±0.06)
[Co(5-NO ₂ -salabza)].2H ₂ O	2.28 (±0.13)	2.03 (±0.11)	1.99 (±0.08)	1.20 (±0.23)
[Cu(5-OMe-salabza)].H ₂ O	2.42 (±0.10)	2.09 (±0.02)	2.03 (±0.03)	1.90 (±0.05)
[Cu(salabza)].H ₂ O	2.08 (±0.03)	2.02 (±0.01)	1.72 (±0.02)	1.58 (±0.06)
[Cu(5-Br-salabza)].CH ₃ OH	1.79 (±0.04)	1.62 (±0.02)	1.43 (±0.05)	1.35 (±0.01)
[Cu(5-NO ₂ -salabza)].0.5H ₂ O	1.72 (±0.13)	1.50 (±0.11)	1.15 (±0.11)	0.80 (±0.24)

Table 2. ΔG°_{av} , (kJ mol⁻¹), values for the metal Schiff base complexes with organotin compounds in DMF solvent at 25 °C

	Me ₂ SnCl ₂	Ph ₂ SnCl ₂	Bu ₂ SnCl ₂	Ph ₄ Sn
[Co(5-OMe-salabza)].H ₂ O	18.77 (±0.24)	18.31 (±0.07)	15.23 (±0.02)	14.89 (±0.37)
[Co(salabza)].2H ₂ O	13.97 (±0.02)	13.75 (±0.15)	13.17 (±0.12)	11.69 (±0.77)
[Co(5-Br-salabza)].H ₂ O	13.40 (±0.97)	11.98 (±0.07)	11.69 (±0.10)	11.23 (±0.15)
[Co(5-NO ₂ -salabza)].2H ₂ O	13.00 (±0.32)	11.58 (±0.27)	11.35 (±0.19)	6.84 (±0.57)
[Cu(5-OMe-salabza)].H ₂ O	13.80 (±0.24)	11.92 (±0.05)	11.58 (±0.07)	10.84 (±0.12)
[Cu(salabza)].H ₂ O	11.86 (±0.07)	11.52 (±0.02)	9.81 (±0.05)	9.01 (±0.15)
[Cu(5-Br-salabza)].CH ₃ OH	10.21 (±0.10)	9.24 (±0.05)	8.16 (±0.12)	7.70 (±0.02)
[Cu(5-NO ₂ -salabza)].0.5H ₂ O	9.81 (±0.32)	8.55 (±0.27)	6.56 (±0.27)	4.56 (±0.60)

bidentate ligand. A tin atom can be located within the plane of the Schiff base phenolic oxygen atoms and is coordinated by them^{2,7,10}. It is useful to mention that, Sn^{IV} compounds are Lewis acids with free coordination sites and their reaction with Lewis bases such as Schiff base complexes leads to electronic and steric saturation of Sn center.

Whereas the structure of these adducts has been thoroughly explored in the solid state^{5-7,10,12}, equilibrium data are lacking, and the range of stability constants for such adducts have not been established. In continuation of our previous studies¹⁸⁻²⁴, with the goal of investigation of both steric and electronic effects on the formation constants and the thermodynamic free energy, these interactions were carried out.

Donor properties of the metal (II) Schiff base complexes :

For elucidation of donor properties of metal Schiff base complexes, eight Co^{II} and Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes were chosen. Two factors may affect on donor properties of the metal complexes :

Substitution effect of ligands :

Tables 1 and 2 shows the following trend for the formation constants and Gibbs free energies :

So far as M(II) Schiff base complexes are concerned, the electron withdrawing functional groups such as bromo and nitro make the Schiff base a poor donor ligand toward M(II) center. On the other hand, the electron donating groups such as methoxy make the ligand more potent donor toward the metal center, although the steric effect of the substitution cannot be ruled out. The more electron releasing groups on the ligands make it a strong Lewis base and therefore the increase in formation constant can be seen. Therefore, *p*-OMe have the highest tendency and *p*-Br and *p*-NO₂ have the lowest tendency toward M(II). Similar results have been reported previously for electrochemical properties of analogous Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, V^{IV} and Co^{III} systems²⁷⁻³⁰. Also, the Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes as a ligand toward organotin chlorides show this property²⁰. In fact, for selected Schiff bases, Hammett type relationships were found between the σ_p values, the *para*-substitute constant and $\log K$ ³¹. Such correlations are shown in Fig. 1. However, since the substituents at positions 5,5' are *para* to the phenolic hydroxyl groups, Hammett-type correlations would indicate that the $\log K$ for the Schiff bases varies as a function of the acidity of the hydroxyl group through the ligand series.

Metal effect :

Co^{II}(salabza) and Cu^{II}(salabza) were selected to study

Fig. 1. Linear correlation between the *para* substituted constants, σ_p , and $\log K$ for copper substituted salabza complexes with Ph₄Sn in DMF at 25 °C.

the metal effect in the adduct formation between the divalent transition metal-salabza complexes and organotin(IV) compounds (Tables 1 and 2).

On the basis of the results, the formation constants for the adducts of $M^{II}(\text{salabza})$ complexes follow the below sequence : $\text{Co} > \text{Cu}$

In the studied systems, metal complexes act as donor. The above trend can be achieved by comparing electron affinity of cobalt and copper. The value of electron affinity for Co (0.663 eV)³² is lower than Cu (1.236 eV)³³. The more electron affinity of central metal lead to decrease of donor properties of complexes and decrease of adduct formation, too.

In addition, the electronegativity (Pauling scale) of the selected transition metals, 1.88 and 1.90 for cobalt and copper, respectively (although is negligible difference), helps interpreting the above trend in the formation of the adducts. The more electronegative metal withdraws electrons and therefore the resulted complex has low tendency to act as donor group¹⁹.

The acceptor properties of organotin compounds :

For study of organotin(IV) interaction with metal complexes, four organotin(IV) compounds (dimethyltin dichloride, dibutyltin dichloride, diphenyltin dichloride and tetraphenyltin) were chosen.

The following trend of acidic strength have shown by Colton *et al.*³⁴ : $\text{SnCl}_4 > \text{R}_3\text{SnCl}_3 > \text{R}_2\text{SnCl}_2 > \text{R}_3\text{SnCl} > \text{R}_4\text{Sn}$. Replacing of an electron withdrawing chloride by an electron donating methyl group compensates some of electron deficiency of the central tin(IV) atom and makes it a weaker Lewis acid. On the other hand, referring to the reported equilibrium constants for interaction of trialkyltin(IV) chlorides with pyrazine we can see a good instance for influence of steric effect of alkyl groups on adduct stabilities³⁵ : $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2 > \text{Et}_2\text{SnCl}_2 > n\text{-Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 > n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$. By increasing in bulkiness of the organo group, the steric hindrance is increased. This parameter decreases the approaching of the acceptor and the donor to each other and decreases the adduct formation. These two factors administrate the acceptor properties of the central tin atom.

On the basis of what has been described above, the trend of adducts formation of Sn^{IV} compounds toward

metal(salabza), as is confirmed by ΔG° (25 °C) and K_{av} (25 °C) values, is as follow :

It is clear that the electron withdrawing groups (Ph) on the tin center makes Ph_2SnCl_2 a stronger Lewis acid but steric hindrance of two bulky phenyls led to decrease of K values with respect to Me_2SnCl_2 . This trend also indicates that replacing the methyl by a more bulky butyl group on the organotin(IV) compound causes a weakening of the interactions. The butyl group can affect the interaction in two ways; a more bulky butyl group makes adduct formation unfavorable because of its greater steric hindrance than the methyl group³⁵. On the other hand, butyl groups have better electron releasing properties to reduce the acid strength of the organotin(IV) Lewis acid. Ph_4Sn has the lowest formation constants due to existence of four bulky phenyl groups.

Conclusion :

By considering the formation constants and the ΔG° of the adduct formation for M(II) Schiff base complexes as donor and the organotin(IV) as acceptors, the following conclusions have been drawn :

(i) The formation constants for a given Sn^{IV} acceptor change according to the following trend due to donor properties of ligands and also metal effect :

(ii) The formation constant for a given donor changes according to the following trend for M(II) Schiff bases due to the geometry, the steric and the electronic factors :

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Salicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-aminobenzylamine, $\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, Ph_2SnCl_2 , Me_2SnCl_2 , $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$, Ph_4Sn , methanol, chloroform, N,N' -dimethylformamide were purchased from Fluka, Aldrich, Alfa Aesar or Acros and used without further purification. The electronic absorption spectra were recorded using a Rayleigh UV-1600 spectrophotometer.

Fig. 2. Spectrophotometric titration of $[\text{Co}(5\text{-Br-salabza})]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) with various amounts of Ph_2SnCl_2 (1×10^{-4} – $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) in DMF at 25°C .

Synthesis of the Schiff base and metal complexes :

All Schiff bases and their Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were prepared and purified according to the method described in the literature^{36–41}.

Equilibrium measurements :

Formation constant measurements have been determined by UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy through titration of the Schiff base complexes with various concentrations of the organotin compounds at $25 (\pm 0.1)^\circ\text{C}$.

In a typical measurement, 3 mL of the metal Schiff base solution (1×10^{-4}) was transferred into thermodynamic cell compartment of UV-Vis instrument and titrated by the organotin solution. The titration was performed with addition of aliquots of the titrant with Hamilton μL syringe to the metal complex solution. The absorption measurements were carried out at various wavelengths where the difference in absorption was the maximum after equilibrium. The final spectra of the adduct showed different absorption bands from the metal complex, while the organotin solutions showed no absorption at any wavelength. As an example, the variation of the electronic spectra for $[\text{Co}(5\text{-Br-salabza})]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, titrated with various concentration of Ph_2SnCl_2 at 25°C in DMF was shown in Fig. 2. The clear isobestic point (305, 348 nm) in the absorption spectra indicates that there is

only one reaction in equilibrium state. The same procedure was followed for all systems.

Molar ratio method :

For performing the molar ratio method⁴², a series of solutions were prepared in which Schiff base complex concentration was kept constant ($1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$), while that of tin(IV) concentration was varied (5×10^{-6} – $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) for molar ratios $[\text{Sn}^{\text{IV}}]/[\text{ML}] = 0\text{--}2$. The spectra of all solutions were recorded from 200 to 500 nm. The relationship between the specific absorbance and molar ratio ($[\text{Sn}]/[\text{ML}]$) for the different formed complexes in solution is plotted.

Acknowledgement

MM and ZS are grateful to Islamic Azad University, Kermanshah Branch for financial support. We also would like to thank Dr. M. Masteri-Farahani for his useful suggestions.

References

1. T. N. Srivastava, A. K. S. Chauhan and Ma. Agarwal, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1978, 3, 378.
2. D. Cunningham, J. F. Gallagher, T. Higgins, P. McArdle and D. Sheerin, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 432.

3. D. Cunningham, J. F. Gallagher, T. Higgins, P. McArdle, J. McGinley and D. Sheerin, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 959.
4. B. Cashin, D. Cunningham, J. F. Gallagher and P. McArdle, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 1753.
5. D. Cunningham, J. F. Gallagher, T. Higgins, P. McArdle, J. McGinley and M. O'Gara, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 2183.
6. N. Clarke, D. Cunningham, T. Higgins, P. McArdle, J. McGinley and M. O'Gara, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1994, **469**, 33.
7. B. Clarke, D. Cunningham, J. F. Gallagher, T. Higgins, P. McArdle, J. McGinley, M. NiCholchfin and D. Sheerin, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 2473.
8. D. Cunningham, J. Fitzgerald and M. Little, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 2261.
9. D. Cunningham and J. McGinley, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 1387.
10. M. Boyce, B. Clarke, D. Cunningham, J. F. Gallagher, T. Higgins, P. McArdle, M. NiCholchuin and M. O'Gara, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1995, **498**, 241.
11. B. Clarke, N. Clarke, D. Cunningham, T. Higgins, P. McArdle, M. NiCholchuin and M. O'Gara, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1998, **559**, 55.
12. N. F. Choudhary, P. B. Hitchcock, G. J. Leigh and S. W. Ng, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1999, **293**, 147.
13. S. W. Ng, *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. C*, 1997, **53**, 274.
14. L. Carbonaro, M. Isola, P. L. Pegna, L. Senatore and F. Marchetti, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **38**, 5519.
15. A. Giacomelli, T. Rotunno and L. Senatore, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 1303.
16. A. Giacomelli, T. Rotunno, L. Senatore and R. Settambolo, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 3552.
17. Y. Inada, K. Mochizuki, T. Tsuchiya, H. Tsuji and Sh. Funahashi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **358**, 3009.
18. M. Asadi, Kh. Aein Jamshid and A. H. Kyanfar, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 822.
19. M. Asadi, Kh. Aein Jamshid and A. H. Kyanfar, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **61**, 1115.
20. M. Asadi, Kh. Aein Jamshid and A. H. Kyanfar, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. NanoMet. Chem.*, 2007, **37**, 77.
21. M. Asadi, Kh. Aein Jamshid and A. H. Kyanfar, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2007, **360**, 1725.
22. Kh. Aein Jamshid, M. Asadi and A. H. Kyanfar, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 1187.
23. A. H. Kianfar and M. Mosalla Nejad, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 3232.
24. Z. Asadi, M. Asadi and F. Mosalanezhad, *J. Iran. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **8**, 794.
25. D. L. Leggett, "Computational Methods for the Determination of Formation Constant", Plenum Press, New York, 1958.
26. D. K. Dey, M. K. Saha, M. Gielen, M. Kemmer, M. Biesemans, R. Willem, V. Gramlich and S. Mitra, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1999, **590**, 88.
27. A. H. Sarvestani, A. Salimi, S. Mohebbi and R. Hallaj, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2005, **3**, 190.
28. A. H. Sarvestani and S. Mohebbi, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2006, **4**, 257.
29. E. G. Jager, K. Schuhmann and H. Gorts, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1997, **255**, 295.
30. A. H. Kianfar and M. Mosalla-Nejad, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 3232.
31. A. J. Gordon and R. A. Ford, "The Chemist's Companion : A Handbook of Practical Data, Techniques". Vol. 145, Wiley, New York, 1972.
32. M. Scheer, C. A. Brodie, R. C. Bilodeau, H. K. Haugen and H. K., *Phys. Rev. (A)*, 1998, **58**, 2051.
33. R. C. Bilodeau, M. Scheer and H. K. Haugen, *J. Phys. (B)*, 1998, **31**, 3885.
34. R. Colton and D. D. Nieks, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **148**, 31.
35. C. H. Yoder, D. Mokrynska, S. M. Coley, J. C. Cotter, R. E. Haines, A. Grushow and J. N. Spencer, *Organometallics*, 1987, **6**, 1679.
36. M. Asadi, M. Mohammadikish and Kh. Mohammadi, *Cent. Eur. J. Chem.*, 2010, **8**, 291.
37. L. Salmon, P. Thuery, E. Riviere and M. Ephritikhine, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 83.
38. M. Sasaki, K. Manseki, H. Horiuchi, M. Kumagai, M. Sakamoto, H. Sakiyama, Y. Nishida, M. Sakai, Y. Sadaoka, M. Ohba and H. Okawa, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 259.
39. Y. Kani, S. Ohba, T. Ishikawa, M. Sakamoto and Y. Nishida, *Acta Cryst. (C)*, 1998, **54**, 191.
40. M. Suzuki, T. Ishikawa, A. Harada, S. Ohba, M. Sakamoto and Y. Nishida, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2553.
41. W. H. Correa, S. Papadopoulos, P. Radnidge, B. A. Roberts and J. L. Scott, *Green Chem.*, 2002, **4**, 245.
42. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 45.